

Thruster and testing facility design developments of low power AF-MPD thrusters in SUPREME and BANTER

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The Institute of Space Systems (IRS) is involved in several projects that aim to advance the applied-field magnetoplasmadynamic (AF-MPD) thruster technology with the purpose of increasing and foster the technological readiness of this electric propulsion type for future application in space. This paper focuses on the latest developments in AF-MPD thruster design and their test facilities at IRS with focus on two European Innovation Council projects: SUPREME and BANTER. The key technologies implemented in the 5 kW level SUPREME thruster are presented, including a high temperature superconductor coil for the applied field generation. The test setup design, which enables the upcoming characterization of the SUPREME thruster, is described in detail. Furthermore, a separate test facility is presented, which was enhanced in order to enable independent tests of hollow cathodes; another key technology of the SUPREME thruster. A preliminary test investigated the temperature gradient over the emitter of a mock-up hollow cathode. The experiment yielded only partly successful results, although valuable insights were gained. Independent cathode tests will be continued further with the SUPREME cathode. Conclusively, first consideration in scope of the recently initiated BANTER project are presented. The project aims to develop a bimodal propulsion system that combines nuclear electric propulsion, nuclear thermal propulsion, and nuclear power generation. It involves the development and characterisation of a 1 kW level AF-MPD thruster with ammonia as propellant. The objective of this experimental investigation is to expand on existing data bases of AF-MPD performance with ammonia and pave the way for the design of a high power AF-MPD thruster for the full scale nuclear propulsion system of BANTER.

Key Words: Electric Propulsion, Testing Facilities, Magnetoplasmadynamic Thrusters, High-Temperature Superconductors

1. Introduction

Electric propulsion (EP) is an established technology in the space industry and is of significant interest for many applications in the emerging space market. The ongoing development and improvement of EP systems within the industry is driven by the need for cost effectiveness, reliability, performance, and flexibility. The two most commonly used EP technologies to date, Hall effect thrusters (HET) and gridded ion thrusters (GIT), are typically operated with xenon or krypton. However, both of these propellants are accompanied by considerable disadvantages in terms of price volatility and availability,¹⁾ and thruster performance is substantially reduced for most of the alternative propellants currently available.^{2), 3)} In this regard, (steady state) magnetoplasmadynamic (MPD) thrusters offer a high degree of flexibility, not only in propellant choice, but also in variability of the operational parameters such as power and propellant mass flow rate.

Another important aspect regarding the application potential of MPDs lies in the development of innovative nuclear propulsion technologies, which offer the promise of enabling unprecedented space missions. Especially, for deep space missions with destinations such as the cis-lunar region, Mars, and beyond the distance to the Sun influences the available solar power, affecting the viability of photovoltaic systems and enabling nuclear energy systems. Nuclear electric propulsion

(NEP) shows significant potential as an innovative propulsion model, primarily due to its utilization of a nuclear-based power source capable of providing both high specific impulse and substantial thrust levels for a suitable EP system. The European Space Agency (ESA) funded RocketRoll project led by OHB Czechspace aimed at harnessing the capabilities of NEP.⁴⁾ Through combined benchmarking and system-level analyses, the project evaluated potential thruster technologies for an NEP-based spacecraft. While missions to high Earth orbits, the cis-lunar region, and interplanetary destinations were addressed with the analyses, a selection of 20 applied-field (AF-) MPD thrusters, operating each at 100 kW power, led to the optimal choice as EP system for the nuclear electric space tug. Possible use-cases for such a cluster of high-power AF-MPD thrusters are given in Fig. 1 which align with the current integration of NEP technologies in European roadmaps.⁶⁾

Following this, MPD thrusters have been demonstrated to show high performance with a variety of alternative propellants, such as argon, hydrogen and even molecular gases such as ammonia. While self-field (SF-) MPD thrusters need to be operated in high power regimes of at least several 100 kW to work efficiently, AF-MPD thrusters can be operated at significantly lower currents and power levels and show the capability to achieve efficiencies comparable to those of HET thrusters. However, AF-MPD thrusters have never been

Fig. 1. Illustration of possible use-case scenarios for NEP space tugs with a cluster of several AF-MPD thrusters.⁵⁾

operated continuously in space and currently still lack the technological readiness level (TRL) to be applied in space missions.

In the past, the major limitations in the development of AF-MPD flight models have been the thruster lifetime and the high power consumption of the applied field generation. The latter is mainly caused by the utilisation of conventional copper coils which are hence limited to lab operations only. These limitations can be addressed by the maturing technology of high-temperature superconductors (HTS). The implementation of an HTS coil can offer the potential to achieve higher magnetic field strengths while simultaneously decreasing the power consumption and the weight of the applied field generation system significantly.^{7), 8)} Within this context, the European Innovation Council (EIC) Horizon project Superconductor-Based Readiness Enhanced Magnetoplasmadynamic Electric Propulsion (SUPREME) aims to increase the TRL of AF-MPD thrusters by demonstrating the integration of an HTS coil into a thruster in the 5 kW power range in combination with multiple other key enabling technologies, further described in section 2. In this scope, a laboratory model of the SUPREME thruster is built and tested at the Institute of Space Systems (IRS*) of the University of Stuttgart.

Recently, another EIC project with a focus on AF-MPD technology has been initiated by a European consortium; Bimodal Ammonia Nuclear Thermal and Electric Rocket

(BANTER). Within this project, a bimodal propulsion system is developed that combines NEP, nuclear thermal propulsion (NTP) and nuclear power generation, all operating with a single working fluid; ammonia (NH_3). In this development, synergetic aspects of the bimodal approach are exploited, such as the mission analysis of combined NEP and NTP and the potential use of regeneratively cooling structures such as the radiator of the spacecraft. As elaborated in section 3, the project scope includes the experimental characterisation of a newly designed low power AF-MPD operating with NH_3 , leveraging the propellant flexibility of this thruster type. The new laboratory model thruster, which is set to be designed for the 1 kW power range, is developed and tested at IRS as well.

The present paper focuses on the challenges and the setup of the test facilities for both projects as well as the approaches to thruster design that are introduced in the following sections. In order to facilitate the operation and characterisation of the AF-MPD thrusters in SUPREME and BANTER, refurbishment and expansion works are being carried out on three existing IRS facilities. In the case of SUPREME, IRS test facility Tank 7 is utilised as outlined in section 2.2. In the context of the BANTER project, IRS test facility Tank 5 is used, which is introduced in section 3.2. In addition to the primary facilities dedicated to full thruster operation, a smaller facility Tank 18 has been expanded with the objective to enable quick stand-alone testing of hollow cathodes. The setup and preliminary evaluations of hollow cathode tests in this facility are discussed in section 2.3.

2. The SUPREME project

The primary technical goal of the SUPREME project is to increase the flight proficiency of AF-MPD technology. As mentioned before, a major advancement in this sense is the usage of an HTS technology in the applied field module (AFM). Therefore, the project aims to demonstrate the operation of a newly designed laboratory model of the SUPREME thruster with an integrated rare-earth barium copper oxide (ReBCO) coil and measure its performance.

The concept of the complete SUPREME propulsion system is shown in Fig. 2. The thruster unit, which is composed of the discharge unit, a thermal management system (TMS) and the AFM, is built and tested at IRS and has been designed in cooperation with Neutron Star Systems GmbH.⁹⁾ The ReBCO coil has been designed to generate B-fields of up to 1.2 T. In the test setup, the coil is cooled to its operating temperature of 60 K with a cryogenic cooling system, developed and built by the University of Twente. Furthermore, studies on flight designs for the propellant supply unit (PSU), the power processing unit (PPU) and the current supply of the HTS coil are conducted by the consortium. In this scope, PEAK Technology GmbH is developing PSU system designs for multiple propellants of interest, Airbus Crisa is developing a

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flight PPU design for the complete propulsion system as well as a custom discharge PPU for the testing phase of the thruster, and the University of Twente is investigating a flux pump design for contact less current supply of the coil in a flight application.

At the current stage of the project, the design of the discharge unit and the TMS are finalized and procurement and manufacturing are in progress. The design of the test setup at the Tank 7 facility, including the custom PPU for the testing phase, has been finalized as well. The following sections describe both the thruster development and the test setup design in more detail.

Fig. 2. Schematic overview of the overall SUPREME propulsion system.⁹⁾

2.1. Thruster development

IRS is conducting research and development in the fields of AF-MPD technology since over a decade. Multiple laboratory models of AF-MPD thrusters have been developed and investigated experimentally at IRS, including the thrusters ZT1,¹⁰⁾ SX1,¹¹⁾ and SX3.¹²⁾ The SX3 thruster, shown in operation at IRS in Fig. 4, has been characterized intensively over a broad range of power regimes up to 100 kW and applied magnetic field strengths up to 400 mT. In the experimental campaign of 2019, thrust efficiencies of more than 60 %, thrusts more than 3.6 N, and Isp of more than 4000 s were

Fig. 4. The SX3 thruster in operation with argon propellant at 250 A, 157 V, 30 mg/s and 400 mT.¹²⁾

measured with argon propellant.¹²⁾ Therefore, the design of SX3 was chosen as the baseline for the magnetic field topology and the thruster scaling to 5 kW in the development in the SUPREME project, as presented in detail in Ref. 9).

However, the SUPREME thruster incorporates key design differences to SX3 in order to increase the technological readiness of the thruster for future flight application. A model of the thruster unit is shown in Fig. 3, highlighting the major subassemblies. The discharge unit is composed of coaxially positioned electrodes electrically insulated to each other by ceramic liners. The design incorporates a radiatively cooled anode made from tungsten and a central mounted cathode. For the cathode, a heaterless hollow cathode (HHC) configuration is chosen utilizing a lanthanum hexaboride (LaB_6) emitter. HHCs provide several advantages for an application in AF-MPD thrusters. These include an increased robustness against component failure, faster readiness for the thruster discharge operation, and a reduced overall cathode diameter.¹³⁾ As shown in Fig. 3, the supply of current and propellant is realized from the back of the thruster. An important feature is the possibility to inject propellant both through the central cathode and through the anode at variable mass flow rate ratios. This has shown a significant contribution to the optimization of the SX3 thruster.¹²⁾

Furthermore, an advanced thermal management system is incorporated to enable steady state thruster operation. The purpose of the TMS is to thermally shield the hot electrodes in the discharge unit from the surrounding ReBCO coil which is operating at cryogenic temperatures. Integral part of the TMS is an assembly of multiple radiation shields surrounding the thruster unit, as shown in Fig. 3. This is combined with a thin-walled structure connection to decrease heat conduction to the backside of the thruster. In addition, multi-layer insulation (MLI) is wrapped around the coil itself to reduce the heat load on this critical component further. Extensive simulations have been carried out to investigate the thermal behaviour and interaction between thruster and TMS and different design approaches have been considered. As a result, we expect that the approach described above enables continuous steady state

Fig. 3. Isometric View of the SUPREME thruster unit and AFM, currently built up for the project testing phase.

operation of the thruster. Nevertheless, it is noted that these results need to be validated by experimental results in the upcoming testing phase of the thruster.

2.2. Thruster testing setup in IRS-Tank 7

The experimental campaign of the SUPREME thruster is performed in the IRS testing facility Tank 7. The thruster is mounted inside a stainless-steel vacuum chamber of 5 m length and 2 m diameter with multiple ports for optical access and vacuum feedthroughs. Apart from the main thruster setup on a thrust balance inside the vacuum chamber, multiple auxiliary systems are installed around the Tank 7 facility. A schematic overview of the setup with all supporting auxiliary systems is shown in Fig. 5 and is presented in more detail in the following sections.

2.2.1. Propellant supply

The propellant supply of the thruster is realized via a gas bottle next to the chamber. The propellant flow is control by two separate mass flow controllers (MFC), which allows the investigation of different propellant flow ratios during the characterisation. Argon 5.0 is used as propellant for the testing phase. The initial characterization of the thruster with argon ensures comparability to the performance of many other steady state AF-MPD thrusters, especially to the performance of the SX3 thruster. The evaluation of other propellants is of high interest for the future development of SUPREME as well, but is not in the scope of the current project.

2.2.2. Electrical power supply

A combination of multiple PPU is used for the power supply of the thruster. A custom PPU, developed by Airbus CRISA, controls the steady-state main discharge at up to 5 kW. The PPU offers a high degree of flexibility as it facilitates thruster operation at full power with voltages ranging from 50 V to 160 V. This is of particular benefit for investigating a broad range of operating regions. Two additional laboratory PPU are utilised to control the cathode ignition process. A PPU with a peak voltage of up to 1000 V for the cathode ignition is connected in parallel to a second PPU capable of supplying up to 10 A at 300 V. The latter is used to sustain the keeper discharge during the cathode heat-up procedure. This PPU configuration has been tested in the preliminary cathode test outlined in section 2.3.

The current in the ReBCO coil, and hence its generated magnetic field, is controlled by a commercial CAENels FAST-PS-1K5 Full 4 Quadrant power supply. The current is defined at maximum 140 A for the coil design by Tokamak Energies. The current leads supplying the coil are closely integrated into the cryogenic cooling system as described below.

2.2.3. Cryogenic cooling system

In order to cool down the ReBCO coil to its operating temperature of 50 K, a cryogenic cooling system is installed at the facility. The system utilizes a commercial cryocooler configuration, consisting of a Sumitomo CH-110 cold head and a water-cooled Sumitomo F70 compressor unit, which supplies the cold head with helium 5.0. As illustrated in Fig. 5,

Fig. 5. Schematic layout of the test setup of Tank 7 showing the vacuum chamber and the auxiliary subsystems.

the compressor unit is placed in the basement floor beneath the test setup, where it is connected to the facility's power and cooling water supply. The position in the basement decreases vibration and noise influence near the test setup and, as a side effect, the large Helium buffer volume caused by the longer supply lines increases the cooling performance of the compressor. The cold head itself is directly attached to a custom flange on the side of the chamber lid, shown in Fig. 9. This flange also incorporates the feedthroughs for the coil current and the heaters for the heat-up procedure after the test. In order to conduct heat from the coil to the cold head, an MLI insulated cold link made from copper is installed inside the chamber. In addition, two copper current links are guided along this cold link with the purpose of ramping the coil with electrical current. These current links are put in thermal contact to the cold link in order to prevent additional dissipation heat loads on the coil.

The cold link is suspended to a support structure on the chamber lid using thin threaded steel rods. The assembly of the cold head, the cold link, and the current links is depicted in Fig. 8 below, without their MLI insulation for the purpose of visibility. Furthermore, an array of sensors is integrated into the cooling system to monitor the operation of the coil. This includes a direct current current transformer (DCCT) to monitor the coil current, several platinum resistance thermometers to monitor the temperature of the cold link and the coil, and two redundant HGCT-3020 Hall Probes to measure the generated magnetic field.

The complete cryogenic cooling subsystem has been assembled at the University of Twente and is currently undergoing rigorous testing in order to characterize its actual performance and validate the thermal models used in the design phase. The setup of this preliminary cryogenic subsystem test is shown in Fig. 6, as well as the vacuum chamber facility used at Twente. Once characterized, the same setup will be installed at the Tank 7 facility at IRS for the testing phase of the thruster.

2.2.4 Vacuum system

The vacuum quality is an important environmental parameter for testing the SUPREME thruster, as literature shows a significant impact of the chamber background pressure

on the discharge and the thrust measurements in AF-MPD thrusters, as described in Ref. 14). This influence only reaches 'negligible levels' at background pressures of less than 0.03 Pa. At higher pressures, it is necessary to quantify this influence in order to gain reliable information about the performance of the thruster. Furthermore, the background pressure has an influence on the cooling process of the ReBCO coil. Since the coil is exposed to the chamber environment, residual particles at elevated pressure values lead to thermal conduction in the space between the coil or the cold link and their respective thermal insulation. This has been considered in the development of the cryogenic cooling system described above, resulting in a requirement on the vacuum level to not exceed 0.1 Pa.

As shown in Fig. 5, the Tank 7 vacuum chamber is connected to the main vacuum facility of the IRS laboratory and, additionally, to two Heraeus DIP50000 oil diffusion pumps located directly below the chamber in the basement. The main vacuum facility and the oil diffusion pumps can be connected to the chamber independently by separate valves (V1 and V2 in Fig. 5). Each of the oil diffusion pumps provide a pumping capacity of 150,000 m³/h for air at pressures below 0.1 Pa. In order to achieve the required pressure levels given by the aforementioned constraints, it is necessary to use the oil diffusion pumps for any test of the SUPREME thruster. Due to the long operational down time of the oil diffusion pumps since the test campaign prior to SUPREME, a substantial maintenance of the system has been performed. This included an oil exchange and a complete overhaul of the control system that is responsible for the safe heat-up and cool-down procedure of the pumps.

After concluding these changes, the vacuum quality in the chamber was tested using two redundant Pfeiffer PKR 251 pressure gauges. The purpose was to gain information about the achievable base pressure as well as the chamber pressure with additional propellant inflow corresponding to thruster operation. The results of this pressure test are shown in Fig. 7. Without argon inflow, a minimum pressure of 0.003 Pa was achieved in Tank 7. When an additional argon inflow is

Fig. 6. Pictures of the vacuum chamber facility (left) and the test setup of the cryogenic cooling subsystem assembled inside (right) at the University of Twente.

introduced to the chamber, the pressure rises significantly depending on the introduced mass flow rate between 0.25 mg/s and 5 mg/s. At the maximum tested flow rate of 5 mg/s, the pressure increased to 0.03 Pa, considering the more conservative pressure measurement. After stopping the argon inflow, the pressure reduces quickly back to base pressure. The results of the vacuum test confirm, that the pressure requirement for the cooldown of the coil can be met, as there is no additional inflow of gas during cooldown. The results also show that for SUPREME's nominal mass flow rates, which are below 5 mg/s, little to no impact of the background pressure on the thrust can be expected, according to the pressure limits reviewed in Ref. 14).

Fig. 7. Pressure curve of a Tank 7 vacuum test with oil diffusion pumps, showing the chamber pressure over time at different argon inflow rates.

2.2.5. Thrust balance & thruster integration

One of the most fundamental parameters in the characterization of EP systems is the generated thrust, from which the thrust efficiency as well as the specific impulse can be derived. As EP systems generally provide a comparably low thrust-to-mass ratio, accurate thrust measurements are critical

to determining their performance. For the SUPREME thruster, preliminary thrust estimates have been conducted in Ref. 9), showing that thrust values between 0.1 N and 0.4 N can be expected at 5 kW operation.

Typically, a variation of a spring-mass-damper system is used for the purpose of thrust measurements. The most common configurations to accurately measure steady-state thrust are hanging, inverted or torsional pendulums. For the SUPREME setup, a new thrust balance is designed and assembled in the Tank 7 facility. An inverted pendulum design is chosen, due to the limited space in the vacuum chamber and the relatively high mass of the thruster and AFM boxes. Two distinct measurement principles are incorporated – a load cell and a distance sensor – in order to ensure redundancy and enable cross-validation of the thrust measurements. A detailed description of the thrust balance development is given in Ref. 15).

Fig. 8 displays how the thruster system will be integrated on the thrust balance inside the vacuum chamber. The single subassemblies of the thruster unit and the AFM are each placed in frame boxes made from aluminium profiles, aligning the thruster to the coil axis. These boxes are positioned on the thrust balance, which is fixed to a support table on the movable lid of the vacuum chamber, as shown in Fig. 8. As a consequence of the positioning on the chamber lid, the setup needs to move with the lid, when the chamber is opened and closed. Hence, all supply lines of the thruster and the thrust balance need to be fed through supply ports on the lid behind the thruster balance. An overview of all of these feedthroughs is shown in Fig. 9. Inside the chamber, the water-, gas-, power-, and data connections are guided from their respective feedthroughs to the fixed thrust balance stand at first. From the thrust balance stand, all supply lines of the thruster and coil are connected to the frame boxes in a manner that minimizes their force influence on the movable thrust balance top assembly.

Fig. 8. CAD model of the Tank 7 lid showing the integrated thrust balance, SUPREME thruster and cryogenic cooling system.

Fig. 9. Overview of feedthroughs and their purpose on the Tank 7 lid.

The same also applies for the cold link and power supply of the HTS coil. In addition, the thrust balance is equipped with a calibration unit that uses known loads to characterize and compensate for any non-linearities, interactions or drifts in the measurement system. This is supported by an actively water-cooled top plate of the thrust balance to mitigate thermal drifts, specifically of its incorporated sensors.

2.3. Stand-alone cathode test setup at IRS Tank 18

In parallel to the work on the main testing facility Tank 7, the capabilities of the smaller IRS facility Tank 18 have been expanded in order to enable quick stand-alone testing of hollow cathodes. The major motivation for such stand-alone tests is based on the fact that an HHC can be operated independently from the rest of the discharge unit and the applied magnetic field. This property is beneficial to mitigate risks in a new thruster development such as SUPREME, as the cathode design can be investigated and validated prior to the first fully integrated thruster test. This section highlights a preliminary cathode test that has been conducted in the Tank 18 facility and discusses its result with an outlook on further stand-alone tests.

2.3.1. Test setup description

Since the hardware of the SUPREME thruster – including its cathode – is still in the process of procurement at the time of this report, a mock-up cathode has been used in the preliminary test presented here. The test setup of this test is shown in Fig. 10. The mock-up cathode has been built in-house at IRS with available materials and processes. It incorporates a LaB₆ emitter inside a graphite tube, and a simple graphite plate that functions as a keeper. The mock-up cathode design is a scaled-down version of the HHC of SUPREME and the emitting area of the emitter was chosen to be comparable to the final design. For the anode, which is needed to sustain the main discharge, a simple copper cylinder is positioned downstream of the keeper plate. All electrodes are insulated from their respective support structure with ceramic spacers.

The primary objective of this test was to investigate the emitter temperature during heat-up and steady-state operation of the cathode. In particular, the investigation focused on a potential gradient of temperature across the axial length of the cylindrical emitter. This is of interest, as the emitter temperature is directly related to the current density, and hence, the uniformity of the plasma distribution over the emitter surface. In order to measure a possible temperature gradient,

two tungsten-rhenium thermocouples (TC1 and TC2 in Fig. 10) are fixed directly on the outer surface of the emitter. This is realised by incorporating dedicated holes in the heat shield and the emitter tube through which the thermocouples are guided. TC1 is positioned 3 mm behind the exit plane of the emitter in axial direction. TC2 is positioned 16 mm behind the exit plane. The total length of the emitter is 20 mm. The temperature readings of both thermocouples were logged constantly.

Subsequent to the assembly of the setup shown in Fig. 10, the cathode was installed in the Tank 18 facility. The facility consists of a vacuum chamber measuring 0.6 m in length and 0.5 m in diameter and is equipped with a two-stage pumping system incorporating a Pfeiffer TPH 270 turbo molecular pump. In order to facilitate the propellant supply of the cathode, a gas feedthrough and a feeding line have been added to the chamber. Argon was used as propellant, which was controlled by a Bronkhorst F-201CV series MFC. The chamber pressure was measured with a Pfeiffer PKR 251 pressure gauge. Using this configuration, a background pressure of 0.4 Pa – 0.9 Pa was measured in Tank 18 at varying argon inflow rates ranging from 1 mg/s – 4 mg/s. The electrical current supply of the cathode and keeper was set up as described in section 2.2.2.

2.3.2. Preliminary test results

The temperature readings of both thermocouples over time are displayed in Fig. 11. The coloured areas in Fig. 11 indicate time intervals during which the power supply of the cathode was on. During the intervals highlighted in red, the cathode did not demonstrate steady state operation. Conversely, heavy sparking was observed during these phases, corresponding to the frequency of the ignition pulses dictated by the ignition PPU. The sparks were identified to originate from within the emitter channel. This behaviour was observed at multiple propellant flow rates between 1 mg/s – 4 mg/s. Moreover, bright flashes outside the cathode were observed during the unstable operation in uneven intervals, indicating some discharges to either the chamber wall or the support structure of the setup. This is backed by the high noise in the thermocouple reading, as depicted in the red areas in Fig. 11. The flashes were observed more frequently at higher mass flow

Fig. 10. Test setup assembly of the mock-up cathode, anode and keeper used in the preliminary stand-alone test in IRS Tank 18.

rates, limiting the cathode operation altogether to a maximum inflow of 4 mg/s.

After increasing the current limit of the keeper PPU, the cathode showed increasing intervals of stable operation, during which no sparking appeared and a clean glow discharge could be observed. However, the stable glow discharge phases were not achieved constantly, and were interrupted by breakdowns accompanied by sparks every few seconds. Nevertheless, no discharges outside the cathode were visible during these phases and the noise in the thermocouple reading disappeared. This is marked by the green areas in Fig. 11. In addition, a clear rise in emitter temperature was measured by both sensors during these stable phases. Furthermore, an increasing difference in temperature between TC1 and TC2 becomes evident at temperatures over 200 °C. Unfortunately, the experiment had to be terminated after approximately 4,400 s due to a side discharge to the chamber, most likely caused by a gas leakage at the backside of the cathode. After the test, the cathode was disassembled. The cylindrical emitter showed substantial signs of erosion on the inner surface which was more pronounced at the downstream opening than at the upstream opening of the channel.

2.3.3. Discussion

Based on the results shown above, this preliminary test did not reach a successful conclusion. The presence of sparks originating from the emitter channel indicate continuous arcing inside the emitter. This is supported by the heavy erosion of the emitter material, which was observed after the test. Given that the arcing did not disappear completely, even after the obvious issue of keeper current limit had been resolved, other causes need to be present as well. One probable reason is that the mock-up cathode is not (completely) gas tight at one or

multiple positions in the back. This is likely the case due to a segmented design of graphite parts (see also Fig. 10). Such gas leaks have the potential to result in an unsteady gas flow leading to instabilities. For future tests with this mock-up cathode, additional sealing between the single components may be incorporated. This effect could be further enhanced by the fact that the keeper was realized as a simple plate in front of the cathode, instead of the more common enclosing keeper design. Both reasons likely results in low gas pressures between emitter orifice and keeper, especially for the smaller mass flow rates tested.

A secondary issue is the potential of a substantial heat loss to the back of the cathode in this mock-up cathode design. This leads to a slow heat-up of the emitter material, resulting in a reduced electron emission even during stable phases. This can be tackled by adapting the cathode design, e.g. by adding thermal barriers, decreasing wall thicknesses and choosing other materials than graphite for the emitter holding tube. All of these measures are incorporated in the final SUPREME cathode, but are not yet implemented on the mock-up cathode used in this test.

A separate issue is the elevated background pressure inside the chamber present at higher mass flow rates, leading to the observed discharges outside of the cathode. Unfortunately, this is a facility effect which can only be mitigated by utilising a vacuum pump with a higher suction rate. It needs to be further assessed, if such a change is feasible for this test setup.

Nevertheless, the test also provided valuable insights. First, the measurement principle was shown to be implemented successfully. The thermocouples on the outer emitter surface provide accurate and responsive temperature readings when stable cathode operation without side discharges is achieved.

Fig. 11. Emitter temperature over time in the preliminary test in Tank 18, measured at two axial positions on the outside of the emitter. Red areas indicate unstable behavior of the cathode. Green areas indicate semi-stable behavior. The current supply of the cathode is turned off in the white areas.

However, it should be noted that this thermocouple positioning does not deliver the actual temperature of the emitting surface but rather the temperature of the outer emitter surface. It is plausible to assume that the emitting surface temperature is higher than the measured value. The growing temperature difference between the two measurement locations still indicates that a temperature gradient over the emitter does indeed appear at elevated operating temperatures. However, the validity of this effect remains inconclusive, as the test was aborted before the emitter reached the expected maximum operating temperatures of LaB₆. Therefore, it is evident that further tests are required in order to assess whether the trend of an increasing thermal gradient continues after reaching steady state operation.

In conclusion, the preliminary cathode test presented here demonstrated that hollow cathodes can be installed and operated in the modular test setup. Furthermore, the temperature measurement using tungsten-rhenium thermocouples was found to be successful. It was found that the current vacuum system of Tank 18 limits the mass flow rates that can be tested as comparably high background pressures are present at mass flow rates over 4 mg/s. Consequently, larger facilities, such as IRS Tank 7, are favourable for investigating the operation of cathodes with higher mass flow rates. Furthermore, the test indicated that the design of the mock-up cathode can be enhanced in a variety of ways, as outlined above. This is considered in the final HHC design of the SUPREME thruster, which is currently manufactured. The experience gained from this test will benefit the upcoming stand-alone test of the final SUPREME cathode.

3. Outlook on the BANTER project

As introduced in section 1, IRS is also involved in the project BANTER which was initiated in early 2025. The main idea of BANTER is to design a bimodal propulsion system using NH₃ as the propellant for electric and thermonuclear thrusters. The performance of the thermal thruster is maximized by the NH₃ decomposition process enhanced inside innovative coolant channels of the reactor. The project objectives to demonstrate the proof-of-principle of this technology involve the development and testing of three lab-scale propulsion systems. Two thrust and coolant channel prototypes are tested in the NTP development in order to demonstrate the NH₃ decomposition and verify the performance increase, and a NH₃-fed thruster is tested in the NEP development in order to evaluate the performance in the high specific impulse range of the proposed bimodal propulsion system. The overall project has been introduced in more detail in Ref. 16). This section focuses on the involvement of IRS in the EP development of the project.

At the time of this report, the BANTER project is still in early stages of system requirement definition. Nevertheless, preliminary considerations in terms of thruster development and test setup design have been initiated. Therefore, the following sections provide an overview of these considerations along with an outlook on the tasks to be performed.

3.1. Thruster development

In the scope of the NEP development in the BANTER project, a full-scale, high-power AF-MPD thruster is designed in line with the requirements of the complete bimodal nuclear propulsion system to be defined. This is flanked by a testing phase, in which a laboratory model AF-MPD thruster is designed and built at IRS. This scaled-down thruster is planned to operate in the 1 kW power regime.

Multiple objectives can be set for the testing phase of the BANTER project. One objective is to utilize the propellant agnostic property of the AF-MPD technology in order to operate and characterize the BANTER thruster with argon, NH₃, and possibly hydrogen. This will expand the existing performance data base of AF-MPDs further with data for low power regimes and for alternative propellants. Such data base expansions can give more insight into the scaling capabilities of this thruster type. This will be highly beneficial for a second objective of the testing phase, which is the extrapolation of the behaviour and performance to the high-power AF-MPD thruster designed in BANTER as well. Another objective is to evaluate the effect of NH₃ as propellant on key technologies of the thruster design, including the operation with a radiatively cooled anode and a LaB₆ emitter HHC.

A further objective is the evaluation of different approaches to the applied field module for low power AF-MPDs. As described in section 2.1, HTS coils offer significant benefits in terms of field strength and mass reduction and are integral for the flight proficiency of the AF-MPD technology. However, an alternative approach of field generation will be investigated in the laboratory model developed in BANTER; the usage of permanent magnets. This is motivated by the small size and the expected lower overall heat loads caused by the low power operational regime. This enables a compact design of the thruster, and hence the AFM, leading to the fact that sufficient magnetic field strength can be produced by capable permanent magnets materials. A major advantage of permanent magnets compared to solenoids and HTS coils is their compact size and simplicity. Since they do not need an additional power source or cryogenic cooling, their demand in peripheral subsystems is minimal, only defined by mechanical and thermal requirements. This is of particular importance for the BANTER testing phase, as the Tank 5 test facility imposes some constraints in size and auxiliary systems which is outlined in the following section. The disadvantages of permanent magnets lie in their high density that can lead to a high mass of the AFM as well as in their inherent difference in generated field geometry compared to a coil generated field. Therefore, the utilization of a permanent magnet based AFM is closely evaluated in the upcoming laboratory model development. This investigation is supported by previous work at IRS on the modelling and implementation of permanent magnets in inductive helicon-based plasma thrusters, presented in Ref. 17).

3.2. Testing facility Tank 5

The main testing phase of the BANTER laboratory model thruster will be conducted in the IRS facility Tank 5, which is a cylindrical vacuum chamber of 2 m length and 1 m diameter, shown in Fig. 13. This facility was optimized for lifetime test

Fig. 13. Picture of the Tank 5 vacuum chamber at the IRS laboratory.²²⁾

of the flight model Arcjet ATOS and the arcjet TALOS.¹⁸⁾ In the past, both of these arcjet thrusters have been successfully operated with NH_3 in Tank 5.^{18), 19)}

As introduced in Ref. 20) and described in detail in Ref. 18), the development of the TALOS thruster has involved the design and construction of an ammonia propellant feeding system. The working principle of this feeding system is shown in the schematic drawing in Fig. 12. Propellant is fed from a gas bottle via a pressure regulator and filter to the gas generator, where the NH_3 is evaporated. Since evaporation of NH_3 causes an increase in pressure, this pressure is further controlled by a pressure controller. The MFC downstream either measures the mass-flow rate in pressure-controlled mode or allows control if required. In its current status, this feeding system is able to measure and control the mass-flow rate and inlet pressure of NH_3 in the range between 15 mg/s – 63 mg/s. For the upcoming testing phase of the BANTER project, this feeding system is adapted to lower mass flow rates required for AF-MPD operation. In addition, investigations are underway to further advance the system. One such example is the implementation of more sophisticated ammonia vaporiser concepts, such as micro channel heat exchangers, as outlined in Ref. 18).

Fig. 12. Schematic drawing of the propellant feeding system used for ammonia and other various propellants.²¹⁾

The vacuum system of the Tank 5 facility is currently equipped with a three-stage pumping system. During the arcjet tests conducted in the past, the pumping system was able to provide a background pressure of less than 0.7 Pa with an argon

inflow of 20 – 30 mg/s.²¹⁾ As mentioned above, comparably low propellant mass flow rates are expected for the BANTER thruster, meaning that slightly lower operating pressures can be achieved with the current pumping system. However, as outlined in section 2.2.5., favourable operating pressures for AF-MPD testing lie in the order of 0.03 Pa. Therefore, an expansion of the pumping system with a high vacuum pump, such as a turbo molecular pump, will be explored in order to achieve a higher vacuum quality.

In order to accomplish the testing phase objectives outlined above, it is imperative that the performance of the BANTER laboratory model is evaluated. Consequently, thrust measurements with this new thruster need to be conducted as well. These measurements will be carried out using a previously developed inverted pendulum thrust stand developed at IRS. With its capability to measure thrust in the range of 50 mN – 200 mN and a resolution of approximately 1 mN, this thrust stand has been developed with the goal to be applicable to a variety of electric propulsion devices characterized at IRS, as outlined in Ref. 22). The thrust stand poses some constraints on the thruster design, in particular on its size and weight. Because of the pendulum arm's load capacity, the maximum total weight of the thrust stand including the thruster assembly is approximately 20 kg and the overall volume shall not exceed an envelope of 60x80x60 cm³ because of the interior chamber size. Both of these constraints need to be taken into account in the development of the BANTER laboratory model.

After manufacturing and assembly of the laboratory model, the performance of the thruster will be evaluated with both argon and NH_3 , which offers multiple topics of interest. First, it allows the direct comparison of propellant influence on the performance of the thruster and its operational behaviour, i.e. discharge stability. Second, the performance with argon can be compared to similar operational points in the low power regime, that are expected to be reached with the SUPREME thruster as well. Especially since both thrusters will likely possess significant design similarities, this comparison can be used to evaluate and validate scaling assumptions and behaviours. Finally, the impact of propellant on lifetime and erosion effects, in particular on the LaB_6 emitter of the HHC, can be assessed for constant thruster design and power regime. Again, this will also be helpful to derive trends in performance and behaviour of the SUPREME thruster with alternative propellants.

4. Conclusion

The synopsis of several relevant projects such as the ESA project RocketRoll and corresponding Technology Development Elements (TDE) and, in addition, EU projects such as SUPREME and BANTER have led to a program line at IRS aiming at the design, qualification and characterization of several AF-MPD thrusters varying in size and power. The aim of this development is to advance and foster the AF-MPD technology for future applications such as orbit servicing, crewed and/or heavy missions accompanied by nuclear power in space developments.

In the scope of the SUPREME project, a novel AF-MPD

thruster is developed that incorporates key technologies needed for space application. The presented design of the SUPREME propulsion system is utilizing the HTS technology for the applied field generation, a central mounted HHC for increased lifetime, and a radiatively cooled anode in combination with an advanced TMS for steady state operation. In order to characterize the thruster performance and demonstrate the functional operation of all of the aforementioned systems, the SUPREME thruster will be experimentally investigated at IRS. For this purpose, the testing facility Tank 7 has been extended with multiple subsystems needed for the investigation of thruster performance. This includes the incorporation of a newly developed thrust balance, a capable cryogenic cooling system, a custom PPU close to a flight design case, as well as the refurbishment of the vacuum system to achieve low background pressures. Both, the thruster assembly as well as the auxiliary systems for testing, are currently manufactured and procured. The first fully integrated test of the presented system is scheduled for early 2026.

In addition to the advancement of Tank 7, plans to exploit the independent testing properties of the HHC design are described. For this purpose, the smaller facility IRS Tank 18 was expanded with the operational capabilities to allow such independent cathode tests. A preliminary test was conducted in this facility on a mock-up HHC that is based on the SUPREME design. The presented lessons learned will be used in upcoming stand-alone tests of the SUPREME cathode, once manufactured.

Furthermore, the recently initiated BANTER project is shortly introduced, which explores the complex design of a bimodal propulsion system combining NTP, NEP and nuclear power generation. First considerations for the test of a small-scale AF-MPD are presented, which will be conducted at IRS in the scope of the BANTER project. The experimental campaign will investigate the performance of the thruster operating with NH_3 . The major objective is to expand existing data bases with data for this alternative propellant, as well as data in the low power regime. As introduced in this paper, the development of this new AF-MPD and its characterisation is based on the broad heritage of IRS in the field of EP development and, in particular, NH_3 testing of arcjet thrusters.

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